

POSSIBILITIES OF USING SOLAR ENERGY FOR CATHODIC PROTECTION OF METAL STRUCTURES FROM ELECTROCHEMICAL CORROSION**Salamov O.,**

*Head of the Laboratory "Conversion of Renewable Energy"
Institute of Radiation Problems of the Ministry of Education and
Science of the Republic of Azerbaijan,
Associate Professor, Department of Ecology,
Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction
Doctor of Philosophy in Physics*

Kasimova S.

*Azerbaijan University of Construction and Architecture,
Department of Ecology, senior lecturer*

Abstract

The article discusses the damage caused to the state due to electrochemical and electrical types of corrosion of metal equipment, as well as ways to slow down and completely eliminate them, which are impossible with traditional methods. Particular attention is paid to the protection of main oil and gas pipelines from these types of corrosion, using a cathodic protection system (CPS), powered by a solar photovoltaic current source (SPCS). If necessary, the system automatically switches from the "cathode" protection mode to the "anodic" one, which ensures a significant reduction in energy consumption, as well as more reliable protection of metal equipment under various operating conditions. The schematic diagrams of the developed CPS, the principles of its operation, as well as the results of experiments carried out on a model installation for various durations of continuous power supply from the CPC are presented.

Keywords: solar radiation, photovoltaic power source, cathodic protection system, solar protective current, electrochemical corrosion, electrical corrosion, metal equipment, reference electrode, protected object, sacrificial anodes.

1. Introduction

Corrosion of metals causes significant damage to the economy. Corrosion losses in industrialized countries amount to about a tenth of the national income. Steel losses due to corrosion amount to 30% of its annual production. Studies show that in the USA alone the annual losses from metal corrosion are 70–80 billion dollars, of which only 10–45% are recoverable losses. 40% of the total steel production in the US goes to replace products that have become unusable due to corrosion. These losses primarily include losses due to downtime, loss of finished products, loss of power, contamination of products, as well as other requirements set above corrosion. A typical example of the latter is the selection of the wall thickness of underground pipelines. For example, the optimal wall thickness of a pipeline with a length of 360 km and a diameter of 200 mm, found by calculation, taking into account possible losses due to corrosion, is 8.18 mm. And when using the appropriate anti-corrosion measures, the thickness of this pipeline can be reduced to 6.35 mm, which makes it possible to save 3700 tons of metal and increase the useful capacity of the pipe by 5% [1,5,8-11,14,15].

In some cases, the amount of damage caused by corrosion cannot be measured in monetary units. This primarily applies to the case when it comes to the human factor, i.e. about permanent loss of health or death.

To protect metal equipment from corrosion are currently used various ways. However, it has been the-

oretically shown that 100% protection of metal equipment from electrochemical and electrical corrosion is possible only with the use of cathodic, and in some cases, tread and drainage protection [2-5,16].

Taking into account the above, it becomes obvious that the development of economically and environmentally beneficial and technically advanced methods and installations for the protection of underground metal equipment, as well as above-ground main oil and gas pipelines from corrosion, become.

2. The relevance of the use of cps powered by spcs in the conditions of Azerbaijan.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan is one of the leading countries in the world in terms of offshore oil and gas production, which are transported overland for further processing. At present, for the direct transportation of Azerbaijani, and later transit transportation of Turkmen and Kazakh oil, to the EU countries, the main oil pipelines "Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan" and "Baku-Supsa" were built and put into operation. And for the delivery of Azerbaijani natural gas to the EU countries, the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzrum gas pipeline was put into operation and the NABUCCO project was prepared for the transit delivery of Turkmen and Kazakh gas through Azerbaijan to the European Union. According to the above, it is obvious that the corrosion issue is very relevant for Azerbaijan. On the other hand, Azerbaijan is geographically located between 39^o and 42^o north latitude and is a country with rich solar energy resources. Table 1 shows the solar energy resources available on the territory of Azerbaijan [7,11-13-15].

Table 1.

Solar energy resources available on the territory of Azerbaijan

№	Name of parameters	Quantity
1.	Solar energy supplied to the land of the Earth's crust, kWh	$2 \cdot 10^{17}$
2.	Annual value of solar energy supplied to 1 m ² of the Earth's surface, kWh	833-2222
3.	The annual value of solar energy supplied to 1 m ² of the horizontal surface of the Earth, kWh	800-2000
4.	Daily intake of solar energy per 1 m ² of the Earth's surface for different seasons of the year, kWh	2,28-6,09
5.	The maximum value of solar radiation observed on the territory of Azerbaijan during the day, W/ m ²	900-950
6.	The annual amount of solar energy supplied to 1 m ² of the Earth's surface in the territory of Azerbaijan, kWh	1850-1900
7.	Number of hours of sunshine during 1 year, hours	2500-3000
8.	Number of working hours during a sunny day, hours: - in the summer season - in the winter season	more 12 near 7
9.	Maximum value of sunny days during the year, days	near 300

As can be seen from Table. 1, in Azerbaijan, the number of sunny days per year is ~300 days, the number of hours of sunshine is more than 3000 hours, the average annual power of the solar radiation intensity (SRI) coming per 1 m² of horizontal area is ~2000 kW/m², the maximum value of the SRI at noon on a clear sunny day is more than 950 W / m², the average number of hours of operation of SPCS, depending on the season of the year, varies over a very wide range [13].

3. Some theoretical aspects of corrosion processes.

There are two types of corrosion losses: direct and indirect. Direct corrosion losses include the cost of replacing (taking into account labor costs) corroded structures and machines or their parts. Indirect losses include: 1) downtime (loss of production during downtime due to underproduction); 2) loss of finished products (leakage of oil, gas, antifreeze, as well as a number of toxic and poisonous substances that can cause explosions and fires); 3) power loss (increase in the power consumption of circulation and heat pumps due to corrosion of pipelines through which the coolant circulates); 4) contamination of products (pollution of water, air, as well as food products, including a number of dyes due to the entry of metals such as copper, lead, etc. into their composition); 5) corrosion tolerances (a typical example of corrosion tolerances is the choice of wall thickness of underground pipelines) [1,5,8-11,14,15].

In developing countries, due to the low development of technological and protective measures, including advanced anti-corrosion systems, the damage caused by corrosion of metal equipment is much greater.

Underground corrosion includes: electrochemical corrosion, electrical corrosion and biological corrosion. Electrochemical corrosion of underground metal equipment occurs due to redox processes of thermodynamically unstable metals in the soil, which play the role of a solid electrolyte. Electrical corrosion of metal is caused by exposure of underground metal equipment to

stray currents from some external electrical installations. At the same time, the sources of stray currents and corrosion are the rail network of electrified transport (trams, electrified railways, including subway roads, ground electrodes in welding shops and substations, etc.).

Electrochemical corrosion of metals occurs by the following mechanism.

In this case, electrochemical corrosion is mainly considered, for which the corrosion rate is expressed by the following equation:

$$i = \frac{\varphi_{K_0} - \varphi_{A_0}}{R + P_K + P_A}, \quad (1)$$

where, i - is the strength of the corrosion current; $\varphi_{K_0} - \varphi_{A_0}$ - difference initial potentials of the cathode and anode; R - ohmic resistance of the corrosive element (protected object); P_K, P_A - polarizing resistance of cathodic and anode processes, respectively (in case of linear polarization).

And in the case of a nonlinear dependence of the current on the potential:

$$P_K^1 = \frac{\Delta \varphi_K}{\Delta i_K}, \quad P_A^1 = \frac{\Delta \varphi_A}{\Delta i_A}, \quad (2)$$

It has been scientifically proven that during electrochemical corrosion, the more corrosive elements are polarized, the smaller their potential difference and corrosion current strength become. Based on these considerations and taking into account formula (1), we can conclude that in order to reduce the rate of electrochemical corrosion, it is necessary [2]:

1) decrease in the degree of thermodynamic instability - convergence of the potentials of the cathode and anode processes;

2) decrease in cathodic polarizability, leading to inhibition of the cathodic process;

3) an increase in anodic polarizability, leading to inhibition of the anodic process;

4) increase in ohmic resistance, which depends on the condition of the soil, its moisture content, aerability, temperature, etc.

The minimum protective potential for steel structures laid in sandy and clayey soils varies within $-0.72 \text{ V} \div -1.1 \text{ V}$ according to the copper sulfate reference electrode. For the territory of the former USSR, including for Azerbaijan, this indicator was adopted $E_{prot.min} = 0.85 \text{ V}$. With anaerobic biological corrosion, the protective potential should be -0.95 V . For structures with a protective coating, the maximum protective potential is taken Safety max $E_{prot.max} = -1.1 \text{ V}$.

However, practice shows that in the main pipelines it is not possible to create the same values of the protective potential throughout its entire length. Therefore, when operating pipelines at the drainage points of cathode stations, it is possible to increase the protective potential for bitumen insulation up to -2.5 V , and for polymer film and silicate insulation up to -3.5 V . Such an increase in the protective potential provides an increase in the economic efficiency of cathodic protection of main pipelines for by reducing the number of cathode stations by 3-4 times.

Starting from the 80s of the last century, many countries began research work on the use of SPCS to power the cathode station. This is due to the fact that during their operation, SPCS do not pollute the environment and do not disturb the heat balance of the near-Earth atmosphere and the Earth itself. They are silent, do not require daily maintenance, reliable in operation and durable (their service life is 30÷50 years). As autonomous power sources, they are indispensable, especially for use in places that are difficult to access and remote from the centralized power supply system, especially in military and other strategic facilities located on islands, mountainous places, and other places with a complex geological structure. Another advantage of SPCS is that they operate on the basis of total solar radiation and therefore do not require a complex system for automatic tracking of the sun during their operation. Further rates of development in photo electricity have shown that the use of SPCS for cathodic corrosion protection of various metal equipment is economically feasible. [3,11,14-16].

4. Statement of the problem and experimental technique on a model facility.

Considering the above, we have created an experimental cathode station to protect main pipelines from electrochemical (electrical) corrosion, which was powered by SPCS. The experiments were carried out in the climatic conditions of Baku. The load current-voltage characteristics (CVC) of the SPCS were taken for different seasons of the year and different values of SRI. The mechanisms of change in the internal resistance of the SPCS depending on the change in load and SRI, the nature of the change in the fill factor of the CVC of the SPCS for various options for connecting individual modules to each other, etc., are determined. Further, the developed CPS was applied to protect against electrochemical and electrical corrosion of the main gas pipeline Sumgayit-Garadagh with pipe diameters of 529

mm. Two-year field trials were carried out. During the test period, the CPS provided an average protective current of 1.1 A, while no noticeable changes in parameters were observed [11].

As you know, Azerbaijan is one of the leading countries in the world in terms of oil and gas production, therefore, for Azerbaijan, corrosion issues are very relevant [7]. On the other hand, Azerbaijan has large resources of solar energy [11-13]. Considering this circumstance, we have carried out a number of studies to study the possibilities of using alternative energy sources, in particular, SPCS to power the CPS, which serves to protect metal equipment and structures from electrical and electrochemical corrosion. For this purpose, a model installation was created, on which experiments were carried out for 50 days. At the same time, steel cathodes in the amount of 40 pieces were used as protected object (PO), and in as sacrificial anodes (SA) - iron anodes in the amount of 4 pieces. Polymer vessels were taken cylindrical shape in the amount of 4 pieces, which were filled with sandy-argillaceous earth with high corrosive activity, taken from saline land plots, along which the main oil and gas pipelines of Azerbaijan usually pass. The mass of earth in all vessels is 10 kg. Inside each vessel, 10 POs are installed, which are located strictly in a circle and in a vertical direction, and one SA is installed in the center of them in the same way. To be able to create the same conditions (uniform current densities, etc.) all electrodes were installed in the central part of the vessel and in a parallel state relative to each other, and to increase the conductivity of the soil, the near-anode sections of all SAs were filled with common salt NaCl. During the experiments, in all vessels, the humidity was maintained at in the range of 15-20%, and the soil temperature is in the range of 20-25°C. The Table 2 shows the primary weights (W_K^0 and W_A^0), diameters (d_K and d_A), lengths (and) and areas (S_K and S_A) of the cathodes and anodes, respectively.

To create the necessary potential difference between the anode and cathodes and the protective current density on the cathodes (in this case, $I_{Prot} = 2 \text{ A/m}^2$), in the second and third vessels, in the immediate vicinity of those cathode pairs that should be removed from the soil last, additional reference electrodes (RE) were installed, which were used as electrodes from CuSO_4 . The choice of these REs is also due to the fact that they do not participate in near-electrode processes occurring between the main electrodes (PO and SA). Since the PO were made of polished steel, the potential difference between the PO and the RE varies within $(-0.72 - 0.8) \text{ V}$. Given this, the appropriate value for the bias voltage supplied from the additional current source to the main electrodes, which is -0.4 V , has been chosen. However, it has been found that in cases where additional chemical protective measures (for example, inhibitor protection, etc.), the bias voltage can be increased by ~100% (up to -0.8 V). And in this case, the potential difference between the PO and the RE was maintained at the established minimum level, i.e. in the interval $(-1.1 - 1.2) \text{ V}$.

Table 2.

Constructive parameters of the cathodes and anodes used in an experimental model plant

Cathode parameters				Anode parameters			
W_K^0, g	d_K, sm	l_K, sm	S_K, sm^2	W_A^0, g	d_A, sm	l_A, sm	S_A, sm^2
250	20	101,2	6355	150	15,6	100	3821

As an additional current source, a DC source was used, to the output of which a storage battery (SB) was connected, operating in buffer mode. For the opportunity maintaining the current density and protective potential throughout the experiment at the set level and, if necessary, smooth regulation of their values, the anodes of the 2nd and 3rd vessels are connected to the current source through a voltage regulator.

The following modes of electrode feeding were chosen. Voltage was not applied to the electrodes of the first vessel during the entire experiment. Voltage was applied to the electrodes of the second vessel periodically with equal on and off times (12 h each) of the current source. Voltage was applied to the electrodes of the third vessel from the SB output, and the current source switched on in a pulsed mode with an arbitrary on and off time. No voltage was applied to the electrodes of the fourth vessel during the entire experiment. In addition, during the experiment, in all vessels, humidity and temperature were maintained at the established level (15–20% and 20–25 °C, respectively).

Every 10 days, the vessels were taken out two electrodes PO, which, after cleaning from corrosion products, were weighed and the mass loss due to corrosion was determined. To be able to maintain the set values of the bias voltage and protective current, each time after the removal of the PO from the vessels, their values were changed accordingly. To clean the samples from corrosion products, hydrochloric acid (HCl) was used, in order to prevent the dissolution of the metal itself, HCl was added as an inhibitor 1-2% formaldehyde solution. On the basis of the obtained experimental data, the corrosion rates were determined by calculation, for which the following equation was applied [1,5,10,11,14,15]:

$$K = \frac{W_K^0 - W_K^1}{S_K \cdot \tau}, \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Graphical dependences of weight loss

where W_K^1 - is the weight of the sample (cathode) after cleaning from corrosion products, g; W_K^0 - is the initial weight of the sample, g; S_K - sample area, m^2 ; τ - is the duration of the test, hour.

To determine the degree of protective action, the following equation was applied:

$$P = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{S_K \cdot \tau}, \quad (4)$$

where - W_1 and W_2 - the loss of mass of the sample during the test without the use of protection and with the application of protection, respectively, g.

Based on calculated data for all four feeding regimes, graphic dependences of weight loss (W), degree of protective action (P) and corrosion rate (K) versus time test (τ). On Fig. 1 presents graphic dependence of weight loss (curves 1, 2, 3 and 4) and the degree of protective effect (curves 5, 6 and 7) on time tests (moreover, curve 1 refers to mode 1, and curves 2, 3, 4 and 5, 6, 7, respectively, to modes 2, 3 and 4), and in Fig. 2 – graphical dependences of the corrosion rate on the test time (curves 1, 2, 3, and 4 refer, respectively, to modes 1, 2, 3, and 4) [15].

As can be seen from the curves, in the second case, the mode of which is close, and in the third case, the mode of which is closest to the power supply mode from the SPCS, operating in combination with another current source, for example, a wind power source (switching on current sources in a pulsed mode), in comparison with the fourth mode, the corrosion rate increases by only 5–10% and 2–5%, respectively, which indicates a high degree of protection of samples against corrosion, and the degree of protective action gradually increases on the 50th day of the experiment. it reaches 81.5%, 86.8%, and 88%, respectively.

Figure 2. Graphic dependences of the corrosion rate on the test time

To determine the feasibility of feeding CPS from SPCS, experiments were carried out on the model installation to study the polarization characteristics of the electrodes. To do this, according to [11,14], four modes of pulsed power supply of electrodes with different periods of switching on and off the current source (τ_{on} and τ_{off} , respectively) were selected, which made it possible to predict the feasibility of using SPCS to power the CPS with arbitrary changes in the intensity of solar radiation, as well as at night hours of the day. In this case, in the first case, a mode with relatively long periods of turning on and off the current source with the condition of maintaining the ratio $\tau_{on} / \tau_{off} = 1:2$ (in this case, $\tau_{on} = 8$ h; $\tau_{off} = 16$ h). In the second case, a mode with shorter switching periods was selected and the ratio $\tau_{on} / \tau_{off} = 1:4$ was observed (in this case, $\tau_{on} = 0.5$ h; $\tau_{off} = 2$ h). In the third case, a mode was adopted with the same periods of turning on the current source, but the periods of switching it off were chosen in such a way that the pause (off time) between each subsequent pulses was longer than the previous pulses. In this case, for the first two pulses $\tau_{on}^1 = \tau_{off}^1 = 2$ h, and then each time the pause time was extended by 0.5 h (in this case, $\tau_{off}^2 = 2.5$ h; $\tau_{off}^3 = 3.0$

h; ... $\tau_{off}^n = \tau_{off}^{n-1} + 0.5$ h). In addition, in the third mode, unlike the other modes, pulses with a variable current amplitude were applied. Finally, in the fourth pulse mode, everything was done in reverse with respect to third mode, i.e. source off time current is selected constant, and the turn-on time of it gradually decreased. However, unlike pre-the previous mode, if after the first series of pulses owls the final value of the protective potential at electrode is less than its permissible minimum level, then the whole process is repeated again. Thus, in this mode, for the time from switching off, $\tau_{off} = 4$ h = const is selected, and for time switching on: $\tau_{on}^1 = 2$ h; $\tau_{on}^2 = 1$ h 40 min; $\tau_{on}^3 = 1$ h 20 min, etc. When the turn-on period of the current source was $\tau_{on}^6 = 20$ min, this is taken as the minimum value for τ_{on} , and such a pulsed mode ($\tau_{off} = 4$ h = const; $\tau_{on}^6 = 20$ min = const) was maintained until the value of the protective potential fell below the minimum level. As soon as the protective potential fell below the set minimum value, a series of pulses was again applied to the electrode and the time of switching on the current source changed again according to the above sequence ($\tau_{on}^1 = 2$ h; $\tau_{on}^2 = 1$ h 40 min and etc.).

Figure 3. Graphics of cathode polarization change for different impulse modes of the current source operation (graphics a, b, c and d correspond to the modes 1, 2, 3 and 4 of the current source operation)

On Figure 3 shows graphs of cathodic polarization changes, respectively, for the first, second, third and fourth operating modes of the current source. As follows from the presented graphs, in all cases, after some time, the protective potential acquires the required value, but in the third and fourth modes, the most close to the CPS power supply mode from SPCS with unregulated output parameters, the best results are obtained, which is also an additional fact confirming the feasibility of using alternative current sources to power the CPS. In addition, a comparison of various discrete protection systems shows that all of them allow you to get significant savings in electricity and when operating with intermittent protection, the state of the

chemical coating remains much better than with permanent protection.

5. Scheme and principles of operation of the experimental CPS.

Previously, low-power SPCS were used as a current source for CPS. [14, 15]. However, due to limited power (at a solar radiation intensity of 900 W/m², the maximum output power of a photovoltaic current source is ~100 W), the operating modes of these control systems were not automated, which led to a decrease in the average daily efficiency of their operation when weather conditions changed. And in industrial VCS, power is supplied from a centralized power supply network, which limits their autonomy.

Taking this into account, we have developed an automated control system powered by a control rod to protect metal equipment from electrochemical and electrical corrosion, which is designed for relatively high power. Depending on the diameter of the pipe, one such installation is capable of protecting a metal pipeline 20 km or more long from these types of corrosion.

Figure 4 shows a general schematic diagram of an CPS powered by SPCS, which consists of SPCS 1, with a maximum power of 700 W, with an SRI of 1000 W/m² [12], a battery pack 2, a controller 3, which is used to control the processes of charging, discharging the battery 2 and connecting its on the load at SRI values below 150 W/m² and at night, control unit 4, operational and differential amplifiers 5 and 6 - respectively, as well as RE 7, PO 8 and SA 9.

This CPS provides for a smooth change in the protective potential in both additionally positive and additionally negative directions, for to achieve which electronic bridge is used scheme 4.

SPCS works as follows. With a decrease in the potential difference between RE 7 and PO 8 to the established minimum level (for RE of CuSO₄ and steel pipe is 0.8 V) per the input of the differential amplifier 6 receives the corresponding control signal, which after some amplification from the output of the latter comes to the input of the operational voltage amplifier 5, to the output of which is a signal with a negative sign. Under the influence of this signal, the transistors of the second arm of the control unit 4, made in the form of an electronic bridge, open. As a result, a negative potential is applied to PO 8, and a positive potential to SA 9, and over time, due to polarization, the potential difference between these electrodes gradually increases and reaches the set value for normal protection PO 8. As soon as the potential difference between PO 8 and SA 9 reaches the set upper limit, transistors VT3, VT4, VT7 and VT8 closed and stopped at the same time voltage on PO 8.

Figure 4. General schematic diagram of th CPS powered by SPCS

As a result of this, over time, the corrosion current decreases linearly, and the protective current similarly increases, and since these currents have opposite directions relative to each other, when their absolute values are equal, the total current in the circuit becomes equal to zero, which means that 100% percent protection PO 8 against electrochemical and electrical corrosion.

In contrast to the existing CPS in the considered CPS, in the case of a deeper shift of the potential of the PO 8 in the negative direction (for example, due to the negative influence of the neighboring CPS, etc.) and jumping its value above the set upper limit, the output voltage differential amplifier 7 changes its polarity. As a result, all transistors of the first arm of the electronic bridge 5 open simultaneously and the system switches to the “anode” protection mode. In this case, a positive

potential enters PO 8, and a negative potential enters SA 9, and the depolarization process begins. Due to this, the potential difference between PO 8 and RE 7 is shifted in the positive direction, gradually decreases and reaches the set value. Further, each time the potential difference between PO 8 and RE 7 changes, on both sides, the above processes are similarly repeated, which ensures guaranteed protection of PO 8 from electrochemical and electrical corrosion.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. To identify the possibility of powering the CPS from the SPCS, a model installation was created, on which continuous experiments were carried out for 50 days. To obtain reliable results, tests were carried out in both pulsed and continuous modes of connecting a current source. It was found that in the pulsed mode the

corrosion rate on the 10th day of the experiment is 12.6% higher than in the continuous mode, then this difference gradually decreases and on the 50th day it is 4.3%. And in the case of using SB, similar parameters are 5.2% and 1.6%, which shows a fairly high degree of protection of the PO from corrosion.

2. The polarization characteristics of the PO were studied under various pulsed operating modes of the current source. It is shown that, compared to the continuous mode, in the pulsed mode, the cathodes (PO) are polarized relatively slowly, however, after a series of pulses, the polarization voltage on the PO reaches a specified protective value. It has been established that pulsed modes provide significant energy savings, and the condition of the chemical coating remains significantly better than in continuous mode. The results obtained show that the use of SPCSto power CPS is quite advisable. And the use of a wind-electric current source as an additional source of energy increases the efficiency of protecting the protected area.

3. The developed SCP is capable of operating in both "cathode" and "anodic" protection modes, and as an autonomous anti-corrosion system can be widely used to protect pipelines and other metal equipment located in hard-to-reach places from electrochemical and electrical corrosion.

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